

UNIVERSITY OF PANNONIA

CoARA Action Plan 2025-2028

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INTRODUCTION

The University of Pannonia (UP) is committed to responsible research assessment, the continuous maintenance of scientific excellence and the highest standards of scientific ethics. Our membership of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) reflects our commitment to implementing and maintaining a research environment that takes into account the diverse contributions of different disciplines in assessing scientific quality, and also to creating an environment that inspires future generations of researchers.

In line with the principles of CoARA, the UP has developed this Action Plan to make our transition towards a more transparent, fair and high-quality research evaluation practice that is focused, efficient and accountable.

This document presents the main objectives and implementation steps necessary to establish the UP's research assessment on the basis of the CoARA principles. By implementing the tasks outlined in the Action Plan and by continuously improving our internal processes in a quality-driven manner, the goal of UP is to create a transparent system of research evaluation that will serve as a reference for regional institutions, inspire and support our researchers and contribute effectively to building international collaborations.

The Action Plan was developed by the CoARA Working Group of UP, which was composed of the members of the Scientific Committee and the delegates of Group of Young Researchers. The progress of the Action Plan will be discussed monthly at the meeting of the Scientific Committee. The Action Plan is shared and discussed by the UP community and approved by the Rector's Council.

The UP is continuously improving its evaluation system, which is reviewed every year.

The review is methodologically supported by the Scientific Quality Analysis Group and carried out by the CoARA Working Group.

Actions (2025-2028)		Status (March 2025)	Responsibility
CoARA Core commitments			
1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research, in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	Incorporation of the COARA principles into the quality policy statement of the university.	CoARA Working Group has been set up from the members of the Scientific Committee and the delegates of Group of Young Scientists.	Rector CoARA Working Group
	Development of a new university employee assessment and an integrated talent and career management system, with a special focus on diverse career pathways, backgrounds (including social conditions, gender, research resources and support availability) and scientific performance indicators (e.g., innovation, patents, tutoring, public scientific activity, practical experience, etc.), including a framework for the recognition of the achievements of staff in research support roles (communication, advice, data processing and preparation).	Steering Committees on academic performance and talent management have been set up.	CoARA Working Group Talent Management Council Steering Committee on Academic Performance
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	We declare that no evaluation will be based solely on numerical (scientometric) measures, but rather on substance and quality. Furthermore, the evaluation should also recognize the sustainability, social, and economic impact of research results.		Rector CoARA Working Group
	Compilation of guidelines for peers assessing theses, job applications and promotions, and for the leaders of departments and/or research groups.		
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	Development of an integrated evaluation and career pathway support system based on a wide range of quantitative indicators (which takes into account the specificities of scientific disciplines). Research evaluation will be based not only on these numerical indicators and related target values, but on a jointly developed and continuously reviewed system that allows for the evaluation of the quality of scientific achievements and career paths.	Steering Committees on academic performance and talent management have been set up.	Rector CoARA Working Group Talent Management Council Steering Committee on Academic Performance

	Actions (2025-2028)	Status (March 2025)	Responsibility
CoARA Core commitments			
<p>4.</p> <p>Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment</p>	<p>In the newly developed university research assessment system, the research organisation will be considered as only one part of the diversity of career backgrounds that can significantly influence research opportunities.</p> <p>We declare that we do not produce internal organisational rankings, we give organisations contextualised targets, set in the light of their own development and improvement, which, even if quantified (KPIs), are continuously monitored for underlying content and we pay particular attention to content-based monitoring of trends (where the trends are evaluated based on the maturity and environment of the research group).</p> <p>We declare that we do not seek to improve rankings positions for their own sake and reject any such activities, especially those that violate scientific ethics.</p> <p>At the institutional level, we do not look at institutional rankings, but at the indicators behind them, and more specifically at the processes involved. We rate the maturity of the development of these processes, and the related analyses aim to support benchmarking activities.</p> <p>Declaration that the university pays attention to the rankings but considers the rankings as a tool for quality improvement only and focuses on substance rather than indicators. Progress in the rankings is only possible through ethically acceptable actions, as a result of quality improvement actions.</p> <p>Development of Recommendations on how to avoid the pitfalls of international rankings.</p>		<p>Rector</p> <p>Internationalisation Committee</p> <p>CoARA Working Group</p>

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CoARA Core commitments		
<p>5.</p> <p>Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to</p>	<p>The institution will allocate resources for the development of an evaluation system and related skills of the evaluators and for the establishment and maintenance of the necessary structures.</p> <p>As part of this work, it maintains a dedicated Scientific Quality Analysis Group, with experts in science metrics and science policy, to communicate with CoARA Working Group and to develop the methodology and management of the scientific evaluation system.</p> <p>Creation of a group talent management within the Centre of Excellence.</p> <p>The institution will also allocate resources for training of evaluators, integrated into the training system.</p>	<p>Centre of Excellence has been set up.</p> <p>Scientific Quality Analysis Group has been set up.</p> <p>Scientific Quality Analysis Group has been set up.</p> <p>Rector Senate Budget Committee Centre of Excellence CoARA Working Group</p>
<p>6.</p> <p>Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes</p> <p>6.1 Criteria for units and institutions</p> <p>6.2 Criteria for projects and researchers</p>	<p>Development of research evaluation criteria for the assessment of research groups and institutions that consider the nature of the unit (e.g. educational or research focus), its fundraising activities, profile, organisational balance and mentoring activities, in addition to the science metrics. The evaluation criteria include the activities of the supporting organisations and the resources available.</p> <p>Development of project evaluation criteria that considers the possibilities of applied research, the applicability of results, local capacity development, and its ability to inspire further research projects.</p> <p>Compilation of a Guide for peers organisational units and projects, and for the leaders of departments, research groups and faculties.</p>	<p>Rector CoARA Working Group Project Directorate</p>

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<p>7.</p> <p>Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use</p>	<p>Dedicated CoARA website within the homepage of Research Excellence Network.</p> <p>In-house promotion of CoARA, encouragement of joining working groups.</p> <p>Research Ethics Committee publishes recommendations, shares experiences, draws attention to negative trends. We believe it is important to create a transparent, motivating and supportive environment, based on open communication, sharing of experiences and suggestions on how to avoid scientific ethics misconduct and self-serving scientific work. In the case of unintentional and systematic scientific ethics misconduct, sanction is of a different nature and it is more important to create solutions and an environment that supports the recognition and avoidance of mistakes.</p> <p>Availability of job and promotion requirements and assessment guidelines on university and faculty websites.</p> <p>Compiling a Guide on how to avoid poor publishing practices.</p> <p>Scientific ethics training for PhD and undergraduate students.</p> <p>Organisation of workshops to introduce the new types of evaluation criteria, to make them more transparent and to collect feedback from employees.</p>		<p>Research Excellence Network</p> <p>CoARA Working Group</p> <p>Research Ethics Committee</p>

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<p>8.</p> <p>Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition</p>	<p>Participation of University of Pannonia in COARA working groups.</p> <p>Participation of UP in European alliances.</p> <p>Participation of UP in national and regional networks.</p>		<p>CoARA Working Group</p> <p>Individual researchers</p>
<p>9.</p> <p>Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments</p>	<p>Dedicated CoARA website within the homepage of Research Excellence Network</p> <p>Semi-annual progress report by the CoARA working group to the Rector's Council. Sharing of report on CoARA web.</p> <p>Report on CoARA at the annual staff meetings by the Rector. This way not only the researchers but supporting organizations are also informed.</p> <p>Annual report for the maintainer on progress of CoARA.</p>		<p>CoARA Working Group</p> <p>Research Excellence Network</p>
<p>10.</p> <p>Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research</p>	<p>Extension of a framework for the continuous monitoring and self-monitoring of the assessment system. The results of monitoring will be available on the CoARA website for evidence gathering and research purposes.</p>		<p>CoARA Working Group</p> <p>Centre of Excellence</p>